

Power Calculations for ILRLE3486/ECON3486 Example Project - Cross-checking: are two heads better than one?

Bart K. de Koning

08/24/2024

Data

We obtain data from a paper by Dániel Horn, Hubert János Kiss, and Tünde Lénárd, titled “Preferences of adolescents—A dataset containing linked experimental task measures and register data” (Horn, Kiss, and Lénárd 2022). We use this data to obtain initial estimates of standard deviations.

```
# Set data URL
base_url <- "https://data.mendeley.com/public-files/datasets/96jt894stz/files/"
file_download <- "d491889f-25df-4aad-a3cb-69ab90116c63/file_downloaded"

url <- paste0(base_url, file_download)

# Fetch data from URL
response <- GET(url)
```

Check if the request was successful and if so, download the data and construct relevant variables. Otherwise, show message that it failed.

```
if (response$status_code == 200) {

  # Save the content of the file to a temporary file
  temp_file <- tempfile(fileext = ".csv")
  writeBin(response$content, temp_file)

  # Load data into a dataframe
  hkl_dataset <- read.csv(temp_file, stringsAsFactors = FALSE)

  # SPiecerate variable indicates how many puzzles participant solved in HKL
  # Create number_tables_correct variable with a cap value of 6 and multiply by 10/6
  # to reflect time available in project
  hkl_dataset$number_tables_correct <- pmin(hkl_dataset$SPiecerate, 6)*(10/6)

  # Calculate number of time_outs
  hkl_dataset$time_outs <- 10-hkl_dataset$number_tables_correct

  # Calculate capped mean time per puzzle to reflect maximum time available in
  # project
  hkl_dataset$time_per_puzzle <- pmin(60/hkl_dataset$SPiecerate, 10)

  # Summarize the number_tables_correct variable
  mean_ntc <- mean(hkl_dataset$number_tables_correct, na.rm = TRUE)
```

```

std_dev_ntc <- sd(hkl_dataset$number_tables_correct, na.rm = TRUE)

# Summarize the time_outs variable
mean_to <- mean(hkl_dataset$time_outs, na.rm = TRUE)
std_dev_to <- sd(hkl_dataset$time_outs, na.rm = TRUE)

# Summarize the time_per_puzzle_capped variable
mean_tpp <- mean(hkl_dataset$time_per_puzzle, na.rm = TRUE)
std_dev_tpp <- sd(hkl_dataset$time_per_puzzle, na.rm = TRUE)

} else {
  cat("Failed to download data. Status code:", response$status_code)
}

```

Power calculations

Calculate the power for the different outcomes of interest. Code adapted from https://github.com/J-PAL/Sample_Size_and_Power

```

power = 0.8 # Desired power
nratio = 1 # The ratio of the size of the treatment group to control group
alpha = 0.05 # Significance level
p = nratio/(1+nratio)

# Construct function to calculate required sample size
calculate_required_n <- function (outcome, mean, std_dev){

  # Expected effect of treatment
  expected_effect = -1

  # Calculate treated_mean under expected effect
  treated_mean <- expected_effect + mean

  # Calculate power
  t_test_power_calc = twomeans(m1 = mean, m2 = treated_mean, sd = std_dev,
                               nratio=nratio, power=power, sig.level = alpha)

  # Explain model results
  cat("For", outcome, "with standard deviation", std_dev,
      "\n we need a minimum sample size of",
      t_test_power_calc$n1+t_test_power_calc$n2 , "to detect an effect of",
      expected_effect, "\n with a probability of", power,
      "if the effect is true \n and the ratio of the treatment and control is",
      nratio)

  return(t_test_power_calc)
}

```

Required sample size for number of correct answers

```

n_required_ntc <- calculate_required_n("number of correct answers", mean_ntc,
  std_dev_ntc)

```

```
## For number of correct answers with standard deviation 2.161117
## we need a minimum sample size of 148 to detect an effect of -1
## with a probability of 0.8 if the effect is true
## and the ratio of the treatment and control is 1
```

Required sample size for time-outs

```
n_required_to <- calculate_required_n("number of time-outs", mean_to,
  std_dev_to)
```

```
## For number of time-outs with standard deviation 2.161117
## we need a minimum sample size of 148 to detect an effect of -1
## with a probability of 0.8 if the effect is true
## and the ratio of the treatment and control is 1
```

Required sample size for time per table

```
n_required_tpp <- calculate_required_n("time per table", mean_tpp,
  std_dev_tpp)
```

```
## For time per table with standard deviation 1.908498
## we need a minimum sample size of 116 to detect an effect of -1
## with a probability of 0.8 if the effect is true
## and the ratio of the treatment and control is 1
```

References

Horn, Dániel, Hubert János Kiss, and Tünde Lénárd. 2022. "Preferences of Adolescents—a Dataset Containing Linked Experimental Task Measures and Register Data." *Data in Brief* 42: 108088.